

Influence of Youth Unemployment on Youth Restiveness: A Study of Jalingo Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates whether youth unemployment has influence on youth restiveness using Jalingo Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria as the study locale. With the aid of the study objectives, hypotheses were formulated in the study. A sample size of 399 was adopted from the population of the study using Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination. The stratified random sampling technique was applied in this study. The summation of all the responses was presented using frequency distribution tables and simple percentages, while the chi-square statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study. The test statistics reveals among others that, there is a significant relationship between youth's unemployment and armed robbery in Jalingo Local Government Area of Taraba State. The study concludes that unemployment influences youths to indulge or involve in restiveness in the form of armed robbery and kidnapping in Jalingo Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. The study recommends among others that Taraba State government, non-governmental organizations, and well-meaning citizens in the state should create employment opportunities for the teeming unemployed youths. Through this strategy, the youths that are unemployed would be gainfully employed and shy away from indulging in armed robbery as an act of youth restiveness.
